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E-Governance And Service Delivery In Rivers State University, 2014-2024

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined e-governance and service delivery at Rivers State University from 2014 to 2024. Anchored on Max Weber's Bureaucracy Theory, the research adopted a descriptive design with purposive sampling of 28 participants from a population of 3,739 staff and 27,917 students. Primary data were collected through interviews and analyzed using content analysis. Findings revealed that e-governance was effective in student administration, staff administration, and financial management but less effective in general administration. It was identified as a key driver of effective service delivery. However, challenges such as inadequate funding, poor infrastructural resources, unstable power supply, low digital literacy, bureaucratic bottlenecks, unreliable internet services, lack of awareness, and resistance to change hindered its implementation. The paper concludes that full adoption of e-governance is imperative for improved efficiency, transparency, and accountability. It recommends that Rivers State Government and the University management strengthen collaboration to provide essential e-governance tools, automate administrative processes, and enhance digital infrastructure, while extending e-governance adoption across all public institutions to improve governance outcomes.

Keywords: E-governance, Service delivery, Bureaucracy theory, Higher education, Digital literacy, Administrative efficiency, Transparency.

INTRODUCTION

E-governance has become an essential instrument for modernizing administration in the 21st century. It refers to the use of internet and information technologies as platforms for exchanging information, providing services, and transacting with citizens, businesses, and between government agencies (Ogbonna, Egobueze, Onya, 2025). Over the past decade, the implementation and adoption of e-governance have gained deep interest among public institutions. The transition to a post-industrial society requires transforming public institutions to meet the demands of the information era. Optimists argue that e-governance ensures efficiency, transparency, and a brighter future for administration. Conversely, skeptics warn that without proper safeguards, it could also entrench corruption or exacerbate inequalities. Scholars like Ogbonna *et al* (2025) view e-governance as an administrative mechanism that improves institutional operations and reorganizes interactions among governments, constituents, businesses, and employees. Some define it narrowly as a digital tool for service delivery; others emphasise that it represents a fundamental transformation of public-sector processes, integrating digital leadership, data governance, citizen participation, and performance measurement.

Recent research supports many of these claims. For example, a global panel data analysis found that higher scores on e-governance indices (such as the E-Government Development Index, Online Service Index, Human Capital Index, Telecommunication Infrastructure Index, and E-Participation Index) are significantly associated with lower levels of corruption perceptions (Mikhaylov, 2024). In Southeast Nigeria, studies show that e-governance efforts have had a significant positive influence on the fight against corruption in public institutions (Nkwede & Nkwede, 2023). Scholars also examine the role of Artificial Intelligence in Nigerian public administration, showing potential gains in efficiency, transparency, and engagement, though highlighting infrastructural, skills, and ethical challenges (Ogbuagu, 2024). Additionally, research presents a consolidated conceptual framework of a smart e-government ecosystem, noting that the maturity of e-government—from government-to-citizen service delivery to more integrated, data-driven, smart systems—is critical to achieving democratic, transparent, and performance-driven public sectors (Alcaide-Muñoz *et al.*, 2025).

Public institutions are among the largest producers of information, making the quality and accuracy of information essential. Digitalization of information through online services reduces errors and strengthens management systems (Chevallerau, 2020). It enhances openness, transparency, and accountability. Open data fosters innovation, stimulates economic growth, and maximizes returns on public investment.

E-governance also reduces service delivery time for both administrators and citizens. Adoption of web-based platforms catalyzes efficiency by streamlining processes and encouraging citizens to engage with government services. Ndou (2024) argues that digital governance accelerates decision-making, improves transaction processing, and enhances internal administrative efficiency.

The economic impacts of e-governance are also notable. Cost reduction and budget savings align with the 2020 Europe Strategy, which emphasizes sustainability and growth-oriented public finances. These savings are driven by the paperless environment of administrative processes, reduced transaction costs, and better control of expenditures (Bhatnagar, 2023). Labour productivity improves through automation, service delivery is cheaper and faster, and e-invoicing minimizes paperwork and delays. According to Abah and Nwokwu (2021), e-governance enables governments to deliver services more efficiently, competitively, and with greater focus on citizens, narrowing the divide between public and private sector operations.

In Nigeria, the importance of e-governance led to the formulation of a National Policy on Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Abdulkareem and Ishola (2021) note that in the early 2000s, the Federal Government introduced digital initiatives to enhance public sector transparency and efficiency. Similarly, Amagoh (2020) observed that while Nigeria began its e-governance drive in the early 2000s, diffusion remained limited. To expand adoption, successive governments launched initiatives such as the E-Nigeria project, aimed at connecting communities, agencies, and institutions. Olalekan, Jide, and Oludare (2021) highlighted programmes such as the National Rural Telephony project, Public Service Network, ICT facilities loan scheme, Internet Exchange Point, and Wire Nigeria initiative.

Despite these strides, Yahaya and Idris (2020) reported that implementation has achieved both successes and setbacks. For instance, e-payment systems replaced manual payment methods, reducing errors and curbing ghost worker practices in the public sector. Nonetheless, challenges of infrastructure, digital literacy, and uneven implementation persist.

In Rivers State, e-governance has been applied within higher education. Rivers State University (RSU) adopted the Student Records Access Management Portal (STRAMP), an online platform enabling students and graduates to request transcripts without being physically present. STRAMP exemplifies how digital systems can simplify bureaucratic processes, improve service delivery, and reduce costs for both administrators and service users.

Rivers State University was established in 1972 as the College of Science and Technology and attained full university status in 1980 as the Rivers State University of Science and Technology, before being renamed Rivers State University in 2017. Situated at Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, the institution is recognized as the first technological university in Nigeria and the first state-owned university in the

Niger Delta. Guided by its motto, *Excellence and Creativity*, RSU currently has a staff strength of 3,739 and a student population of 27,917 (Office of the Registrar, Establishment Division & ICT Center, Rivers State University, 2024). Instruction is delivered in English, and the university continues to adopt ICT-driven systems to enhance both academic and administrative service delivery. Against this backdrop, the paper titled “*E-Governance and Service Delivery in Rivers State University, 2014–2024*” was conceived, positioning e-governance as a critical driver of efficiency, accountability, and transparency in Nigeria’s higher education sector. Accordingly, the paper poses the research question: **How has e-governance impacted service delivery in Rivers State University?**

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The paper adopted Bureaucracy Theory by Max Weber (1864–1920). The term *bureaucracy* was first coined in 1745 by Vincent de Gournay, a French economist, who combined the word *bureau* (meaning writing table or office) with the Greek suffix for “rule,” to signify the *rule of officials*. Max Weber later provided a more precise definition, recommending bureaucracy as the most effective administrative form for achieving organizational goals. He argued that bureaucracy represents a distinct system of administration that promotes order, efficiency, and predictability in organizational life.

As the father of bureaucratic organizational theory, Weber criticized informal, family-like structures where authority was poorly defined, arguing that such systems hindered organizational success. He proposed instead a formal and rigid structure—bureaucracy—where rules, legitimate authority, and competence form the foundation of administration. Weber emphasized that power should derive from one’s official position, professional competence, and adherence to explicit rules rather than from personal relationships.

Weber further argued that bureaucracy should manage its affairs through legal instruments, ensuring law and order, revenue generation, efficient service delivery, and public satisfaction. According to Weber (1947), the *ideal bureaucracy* is characterized by:

1. **Division of Labor and Specialization** – clear division of tasks into specialized roles, each with authority to perform its duties.
2. **Rules and Regulations** – consistent systems of abstract rules that ensure uniformity and standardization.
3. **Hierarchy of Authority** – a structured chain of command, where lower offices are subject to higher ones.
4. **Impersonality** – administrators maintain social distance to ensure rational, unbiased decision-making.
5. **Career Orientation** – employment and promotion based on qualifications and performance, protecting employees from arbitrary dismissal and fostering loyalty.

Application of Bureaucracy Theory to the paper

Ugben and Egobueze (2021) observe that the university system is inherently bureaucratic, much like other public institutions. Bureaucracy, they argue, is indispensable for organizational survival. Similarly, Davies, Nsiegbe, and Elike (2024) define bureaucracy as the structures, procedures, and regulations that guide organizations toward effective functioning, particularly in education. These scholars note that bureaucratic principles in schools, colleges, and universities ensure administrative clarity, academic standards, and efficient resource management. Accordingly, the scholars argued that bureaucracy remains the most effective organizational model for enhancing administrative efficiency in the public service and continues to be widely adopted in large-scale systems. Its mechanisms like hierarchy, rules, impersonality, and division of labor that are evident in the university’s structure. Davies, Nsiegbe, and Elike (2024) again add that these principles help to establish clear lines of authority and standardized procedures, thus supporting effective decision-making processes.

Furthermore, they emphasized that public service rules on recruitment, promotion, staff motivation, and discipline are rooted in bureaucratic principles of merit, seniority, and achievement. They highlight division of labor as central to productivity: departments or units function as subsystems coordinated to achieve overall institutional objectives. Motivation, identified by Idakwoji and Stephen (cited in Uben & Egobueze, 2021), is another cardinal element of bureaucracy, enabling employees to enthusiastically perform their duties despite challenges.

In the context of the university, division of work ensures staff deploy their skills and knowledge effectively, while motivation policies, if properly implemented, can significantly enhance performance and service delivery. These features underscore the bureaucratic nature embedded in the university system and its role in promoting productivity, accountability, and efficiency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted a descriptive research design, which, according to Williams (2007), examines attributes of a phenomenon based on observation. The design provided a detailed picture of the population and helped identify patterns, trends, and relationships, thereby deepening understanding of e-governance and service delivery.

The paper population comprised 3,739 staff and 27,917 students of Rivers State University, totaling 31,656 (Office of the Registrar, Establishment Division, Cinfores Ltd & ICT Center, 2024). From this, 28 participants (13 staff and 15 students) were selected. Following Creswell (2013), purposive sampling was employed to obtain rich, in-depth data from participants with relevant knowledge. As Patton (2015) emphasized, quality of information is more important than sample size.

Both primary and secondary data were used. Primary data came from interviews with staff and students, while secondary data were drawn from journals, textbooks, newspapers, and reports. Interviews followed Patton's (2002) recommendation of combining informal conversations with open-ended questions. Consent forms and interview guides were distributed, with two weeks given for participants to prepare. Interviews were conducted face-to-face, and responses were recorded with consent.

Validity was established through face and content validation. The instrument was reviewed by supervisors and senior lecturers to ensure clarity and relevance (Baridam, 2015). Reliability was tested using replicability, ensuring consistent reproduction of findings (Cresswell & Cresswell, 2017; Nosek, 2015). Data were analyzed using qualitative content analysis to identify themes, patterns, and categories (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). This approach enabled interpretation of meanings and relationships within responses, consistent with Patton's (2002) view of content analysis as qualitative data reduction and sense-making.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

DATA PRESENTATION

The researcher tactfully and deliberately planned to interview 13 staff members and 15 students to sum up 28 participants relevant to the paper. However, due to the busy schedule of some intended participants the researcher was able to ultimately interview 8 staff members and 13 students aggregating to 21 individuals found pertinent to the paper in Rivers State University.

Research Question: *How has e-governance impacted service delivery in Rivers State University?*

Interviews revealed that e-governance has significantly transformed service delivery in Rivers State University (RSU) across student administration, staff management, information dissemination, and academic services.

An Administrative Officer, Kogbara Emmanuel Baridobi, explained that e-governance supports student admissions, personal data management, submission of assignments, plagiarism checks, staff recruitment, payroll, and nominal roll updating (personal communication, January 14, 2025). Similarly, West Samuel Tuboibibo from the Faculty of Media and Communication Studies emphasized that the system enhances

transparency and accessibility of information, allowing students and the public, whether within or outside Nigeria to access university services online (personal communication, January 14, 2025).

Staff also noted governance benefits. Peace Igwe (Faculty of Education) highlighted that e-governance promotes transparency and accountability, curbing financial mismanagement while improving service quality and boosting student enrollment (personal communication, January 14, 2025). Prince Iheanyi Nwabali (Faculty of Engineering) added that the system reduces costs, increases efficiency, and enables participatory engagement by informing, consulting, and involving students (personal communication, January 14, 2025).

Specific services have also been enhanced. Dr. A.D. Ogbuleka described how RSU uses e-governance to manage JAMB examinations, conduct student elections electronically, operate an ICT Academy accredited by Microsoft and CISCO, and run anti-plagiarism software like Turnitin (personal communication, January 16, 2025). Grace Damiete George noted improvements in online registration, eCampus payments, and transcript production through the Cinfores Help Desk (personal communication, January 16, 2025). Isaiah Emeka Ekine confirmed the efficiency of online registration systems, which secure student records and eliminate paper-based risks (personal communication, January 16, 2025).

Students also testified to positive impacts. Omereji Glory Uloma (400-level, Humanities) and Ojigini Precious Umanunim (200-level) described how e-governance enables remote payment of fees, online course registration, and secure publication of results via personalized dashboards (personal communication, January 20, 2025). Peace Odogu (400-level, Humanities) observed that the automation of admissions, Post-UTME grading, and transcript management saves time and reduces paperwork (personal communication, January 20, 2025).

Other students reinforced these views. Nwaogbo Prince Chukwuemeka praised the ease of online fee payments and library e-services (personal communication, January 20, 2025). Dimkpa Emmanuel stressed the convenience of applying for transcripts and certificates remotely (personal communication, January 22, 2025). Owhonda Felisha Chiburoma noted that student elections are now transparent, thanks to electronic voting (personal communication, January 22, 2025). Bariagara Goodluck Tombari described the shift from manual aptitude tests to Computer-Based Tests (CBT), which deliver instant and transparent results (personal communication, January 22, 2025).

Furthermore, Onwubikwo Vivian Chizoba emphasized that information dissemination has moved from campus notice boards to online platforms, making RSU news globally accessible (personal communication, January 22, 2025). Stella Ezekwu (100-level, Education) and Joshua Chidozie (Postgraduate, Sciences) highlighted improvements in Post-UTME automation, UTME hosting, and student data management via eCampus (personal communication, January 24, 2025).

Finally, Ogbonna Esther (500-level, Engineering) and Atiemie Dappa (Postgraduate, Environmental Sciences) confirmed that e-governance facilitates secure database management, efficient information retrieval, and modernized library services that better meet user needs (personal communication, January 24, 2025).

Overall, testimonies demonstrate that e-governance at RSU has improved transparency, reduced corruption, increased efficiency, and enhanced access to academic and administrative services for both staff and students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Impact of E-Governance on Service Delivery in Rivers State University

The core aim of incorporating e-governance in public institutions like Rivers State University is to enhance service delivery. The paper discovered that e-governance in Rivers State University is responsible for the provision of effective services to the people. This system achieves this ranking by transforming traditional means of service delivery into a contemporary pattern in the University. This transformational impact is underpinned and exemplified in the following:

Post-Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination

E-governance has successfully transformed the conduct of the Post-UTME examination from the traditional paper-pencil test (PPT) to computer-based test (CBT) in the University. Akiri Samuel, a participant, revealed that the computer-based test (CBT) is sacrosanct and functions perfectly in Rivers State University. This process ensures transparency and eliminates errors associated with script marking and result publishing in the University. Bariagara Goodluck Tombari agreed with Akiri Samuel and explained that the interesting part of CBT is that it has eliminated time wastage and ensured transparency in the Post-UTME examination. The conduct of the examination, marking, and release of results have been computerized. It is now possible for students to see their Post-UTME results at the end of their respective examinations before leaving the examination hall. Stella Ezekwu, a student participant, said: *"When I wrote my Post-UTME here, the materials used for the examination were computers, and the result was automated immediately I finished and submitted."* This was not possible in the past when the examination was paper-pencil based. The PPT mode was reportedly characterized by massive irregularities and inefficiency, which necessitated a paradigm shift. Although the paradigm shift has its own share of advantages and disadvantages, general improvement over the traditional PPT mode has been achieved.

Admission Automation

Admission of students into the University has also been automated in line with contemporary demands. Prior to this, admission processes were handled manually with pen and paper, which was very slow, required much effort, and was time-consuming. Operations such as searching for student data or modifying student records were difficult, as each modification had to be overwritten or recorded elsewhere. This process was characterized by ambiguity. Today, the admission process has been automated through e-governance. Students can now view their admission status via their personalized e-application account. This was corroborated by Stella Ezekwu, who stated that a Post-UTME examinee can easily ascertain his or her admission status by checking a personalized eCampus account on the University web domain. Admitted students can also proceed to the e-registration portal for registration by navigating through their e-application dashboard on the University's eCampus domain.

E-Application

Rivers State University has made tremendous progress in transforming how application forms are purchased. In the past, people needed to visit banking halls within the University environment to obtain forms. Now, this is done electronically anywhere in the world using the e-application system. Bariagara Goodluck Tombari revealed that the University uses e-governance to provide services such as online application for programs of paper. Nwaogbo Prince Chukwuemeka, a student participant, confirmed this when he explained that he applied for a course of paper through the University website.

The same mechanism applies to transcript applications using STRAMP, which enables graduates of the University to request transcripts online without having to be physically present. The system also applies to certificate production. Dimkpa Emmanuel confirmed that graduates can apply for their certificates and transcripts from anywhere in the world using an electronic internet-enabled device with a stable connection. The University provides a mechanism through which graduates can request their transcripts and certificates by applying via their personalized eCampus account.

E-Payment and E-Invoicing

E-payment ensures that students can pay their school charges via their personalized eCampus account and receive receipts electronically through the same channel. Omereji Glory Uloma, a student participant, said: *"E-governance has made things easier for us as we can actually carry out certain activities using our phones in our homes, for example, the payment of school fees."* Nwaogbo Prince Chukwuemeka agreed, stating that students can conduct essential tasks such as paying tuition fees through the University web domain. E-governance allows students to pay fees from the comfort of their homes or hostels. This process is enhanced through e-payment gateways incorporated into each student's personalized e-registered account on the University eCampus domain.

E-Registration

This facility ensures that students can register online via the University's eCampus domain. It simplifies the registration process using a web-enabled, user-friendly wizard and digitizes supporting documents through intuitive processes and tools. Joshua Chidozie affirmed that students conduct registration electronically through their personalized accounts on the University's eCampus domain. The e-registration solution allows the University to focus less on paperwork and more on meeting the educational needs of students, using a cost-efficient, secure process that allows easy access to student files.

Isaiah Emeka Ekine also revealed the effectiveness of the e-registration process empowered by e-governance, noting that it eliminates the need for manually filling paper forms and sending them to registration offices. The e-registration system has solved problems associated with manual operations, such as difficulty in updating records, challenges retrieving lost bursary receipts, and the inability of students to remotely register or access documents such as fee receipts.

E-Result

The deployment of e-governance has made e-results possible in Rivers State University. Students testified that the effectiveness of e-governance in results publishing aligns with modern demands. Ojigini Precious Umanunim explained that results are now published electronically on the University eCampus website. Omereji Glory Uloma added that students can access academic results via their personalized accounts on the eCampus domain. Previously, results were published on physical boards within the University campus. These were often destroyed after a few days or weeks. With e-results, students can access their academic records whenever needed.

Electronic Data Management

Data management for students and staff has also been enhanced electronically. Ogbonna Esther emphasized that e-governance makes data retrieval easier and safer compared to paper files. Electronic Data Management (EDM) was introduced to automate the tracking and monitoring of student and staff information. The system uses cataloguing services for file search and indexing to improve availability and quality of data. Key elements of EDM include fast retrieval, organized filing, quality records, and a centralized databank. The system also provides simple, accurate transmission of data files for monitoring and tracking.

E-Library

E-governance has also enabled e-library services. Nwaogbo Prince Chukwuemeka observed that the University library has a section where students and faculty can access computers to gather information from the internet for academic purposes. The library, once a physical structure limited to campus, has evolved into a virtual platform that is globally accessible. Atiemie Dappa stated that e-governance has made library services more efficient and convenient, meeting the needs of users with ease. In the past, the library contained only physical collections such as books, journals, and magazines. Today, it integrates physical and digital resources, disseminating and preserving knowledge electronically through e-governance.

Electronic Dissemination of Information

Information circulation has been transformed by e-governance. Previously, University announcements were posted on notice boards, which forced the public to travel to campus at additional cost. E-governance has removed this barrier. West Samuel Tuboibibo revealed that University information and services are now more available and less costly, as they can be accessed online globally. Prince Iheanyi Nwabali, a staff participant, added that e-governance has enabled a transition from passive access to active student participation by informing, representing, encouraging, consulting, and involving them. Onwubikwo Vivian Chizoba confirmed that information of public interest is disseminated on the University's web domain, making it more accessible to the wider public.

E-Election and E-Voting

This mechanism enables students to vote electronically for candidates to represent them at the University Senate level. Owhonda Felisha Chiburoma revealed that SUG elections in the University are governed by e-governance. The system has eliminated malpractices, and electorates now feel valued because their votes count.

Turnitin Facility

This internet-based anti-plagiarism software checks for possible cases of plagiarism. According to Dr. A.D. Ogbuleka, “*the system assists in assessing the originality of a report (dissertation/thesis) and interpreting the originality of the report.*” The most important feature of the software is its ability to check originality against a broad database of authenticated scholarly content, generate a similarity report, indicate sources, and quantify overlaps in percentages

E-governance modernizes conventional governance in Rivers State University through the use of ICT facilities and applications to improve service delivery to the public. Umar and Ikechukwu (2022) noted that e-governance is an enabler and a key instrument for effective service delivery through ICT adoption. Service delivery is about meeting public needs quickly and conveniently. When this happens, effectiveness and efficiency are achieved. E-governance is thus rated capable and effective in ensuring that the demands of stakeholders at Rivers State University are met. This finding confirms the view of Olalekan and Olidare (2021), that service delivery is the provision of services of public interest to citizens.

CONCLUSION

E-governance is a *sine qua non* for improving service delivery in both public and private institutions. It has the capacity to transform ineffective approaches into efficient methods of providing services to the populace. The adoption and deployment of e-governance ensure that public services are delivered in a timely and effective manner.

Globally, the world has transitioned from the industrial age to the information age, and it is now gradually shifting toward the knowledge age, marked by the rise of artificial intelligence (AI). It is therefore imperative for public institutions to recognize this transformation and adopt e-governance practices that incorporate innovative technologies. Doing so will not only guarantee bureaucratic continuity and effective service delivery but will also help mitigate inefficiencies and administrative bottlenecks.

Transparency and accountability remain key demands from citizens who wish to see public resources prudently utilized. These elements are best achieved through effective e-governance mechanisms. Thus, it is essential for governments and public institutions to embrace e-governance systems to foster public trust. Transparency serves as a quintessential democratic value that underpins trustworthy, high-performing, and accountable governance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the paper, the following recommendations are made:

1. Strengthen inter-institutional cooperation:

The Rivers State Government and the Management of Rivers State University should strengthen synergistic cooperation in providing essential e-governance tools across administrative offices. This will enable the automation of routine office tasks, facilitate efficient inter-office e-communication, and significantly reduce bureaucratic bottlenecks. Ultimately, such reforms will lead to more effective, transparent, and responsive administrative service delivery.

2. Enhance e-learning and distance education infrastructure:

The Rivers State Government and the University should collaborate to provide robust e-learning infrastructure and distance education facilities. Such collaboration is crucial for the cybernation of the educational process, enabling high-quality pedagogy and scholarly engagement remotely. By embracing

digital learning systems, the University will enhance accessibility, inclusivity, and resilience in service delivery.

3. Adopt advanced e-security systems:

The Management of Rivers State University should transition from traditional security systems to a technology-driven e-security framework as part of its e-governance strategy. This includes installing modern surveillance systems, digital access controls, and real-time monitoring to reduce theft, robbery, and unauthorized access—particularly in student hostels. Integrating e-security will also help curb cult-related activities within the University. On a broader scale, government adoption of e-policing and digital security infrastructure will reduce terrorism and criminality, ensuring a safer society.

4. Develop supportive policies and infrastructure:

The Rivers State Government and the University should jointly develop and implement policies while providing the necessary infrastructure and resources to support e-governance initiatives. Such coordinated efforts are vital to overcoming adoption challenges and ensuring that both society and the university community benefit from improved efficiency, transparency, and service delivery in the digital age.

5. Bridge the digital literacy gap:

The Management of Rivers State University should establish and empower a dedicated team of qualified personnel to train staff and students on the effective use of e-governance systems. This will help bridge the digital literacy gap, enhancing administrative efficiency, transparency, and equitable access to digital resources.

6. Integrate e-governance into teaching and learning:

The University, in collaboration with the Rivers State Government, should integrate e-governance tools into classroom practices, gradually replacing traditional teaching methods. This digital transformation has the potential to significantly improve pedagogical effectiveness and strengthen the overall academic enterprise.

REFERENCES

- Abdulkareem, H. & Ishola, E. (2021). Critique of Public Administrative Reform Systems: Post Independence in Nigeria. *Africas public Service Delivery & Performance Reviewed*, 4(1), 346-360.
- Alcaide-Muñoz, L., Bolívar, M. P. R., Criado, J. I., & Sandoval-Almazán, R. (2025). Smart e-government ecosystems: A conceptual framework for digital transformation. *Electronic Government, an International Journal*, 21(1), 1–20.
- Backus T.L (2021). Business Unit Level Between Employee Satisfaction, Employee Engagement and Business Outcomes: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(12), 268-279.
- Baridam, D. M. (2015). *Research methods in administrative sciences*. Lagos: Sherbrooke Associates.
- Bhatnagar, S. (2023). *The economic and social impact of e-government*. A background paper for UNDESA publication: *E-government, the citizens and the state: Debating governance in the information age*. World Public Sector Report, United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs.
- Chevallerau, F. (2020). *The impact of e-government on competitiveness, growth and jobs*. Background research paper. The IDABC eGovernment Observatory of the European Communities.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Davies, E., Nsiegebe, G. and Elike J. (2024), Bureaucratic Structures and Service Delivery in Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2010 - 2023. *Journal of Public Administration and Social Welfare Research*, 9 (1), 38 - 55.

- Hsieh, H. F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative Health Research*, 15(9), 1277-1288.
- Mikhaylov, S. J. (2024). E-governance and corruption: Evidence from global panel data analysis. *Future Business Journal*, 10(3), 1–16.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis: An Expanded Sourcebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Ndou, V. (2024). E-government for developing countries: opportunities and challenges. *The Electronic Journal on Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 18(1), 1-24.
- Nkwede, J. O., & Nkwede, G. O. (2023). E-governance and the fight against corruption in Nigeria: An appraisal. *Nigerian Journal of Social Policy*, 4(2), 155–170.
- Nosek, B. A., Alter, G., Banks, G. C., Borsboom, D., Bowman, S. D., Breckler, S. J., Yarkoni, T. (2015). Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science. *Science*, 349(6251), aac4716.
- Ogbonna, B. N., Egobueze, A., & Onya, R. (2025). *Digital innovations and electoral governance in Nigeria: Evaluating the 2023 presidential election in Rivers State*. *International Journal of Innovative Development & Policy Studies*, 13(3), 174 - 188.
- Ogbonna, B. N., Egobueze, A., Onya, R., & Owzor, N. (2025). Technology, democracy, and election credibility: An appraisal of e-governance in Nigeria's 2023 presidential polls in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Legal & Political Studies*, 13(3), 149–163.
- Ogbuagu, C. (2024). Artificial intelligence and e-governance: Opportunities and challenges in Nigeria's public administration. *ASRIC Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(1), 45–62.
- Olalekan, Jide, R. & Oludare (2021). The Use of Computer Based Testing Method for the Conduct of Examination at the University of Ilorin. *International Journal of Learning & Development*, 2(3)
- Olalekan, O. I. & Oludare, B. (2021). "E-Government in Nigeria: Benefits, Problems and Future Prospects", *Nigerian Journal of Public Administration and Local Government*, XIII (1), 127 - 133.
- Patton, M.Q. (2002). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods*. (3rd ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage